

Electrochemical Characteristics of *N*-Phenylmonoamide Derivatives of some 1,2-Dicarboxylic Acids

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Electrochemical investigations have been carried out on a few NaL systems by cyclic voltammetric and coulometric techniques, where HL's are *N*-phenylmonoamide derivatives of 1,2-dicarboxylic acids (1), on mercury electrode in a buffered aqueous media (pH range 6-12) at room temperature (25°). Only the maleic acid derivatives respond electrochemically in the potential range 0.00 to (-)2.00 V vs Ag/AgCl, yielding pH-dependent irreversible electron transfer profiles in the potential range (-)1.00 to (-)1.60 V, whereas the phthalic and succinic acid derivatives are electrochemically quiet even up to (-)2.00 V. A plausible pH-dependent mechanism for the CV profiles of the maleic acid derivatives is suggested. The diffusion coefficients of the L⁻ systems are calculated.

N-Phenylmonoamide derivatives of some 1,2-dicarboxylic acids (HL, shown in structure 1) are found to have noteworthy fungicidal and herbicidal properties^{1,2} and their coordination compounds are extensively studied³⁻⁶. Yet no electrochemical investigations of these systems are available in the literature. We present here the first report of the electrochemical studies of the aqueous solutions of their sodium salts, NaL.

Results and Discussion

The cyclic voltammograms, recorded for the NaL aqueous solutions at different pH's, reveal that only maleic acid derivatives give two successive irreversible reduction waves and the positions of the peak potentials are pH-dependent,

whereas the phthalic and succinic analogues do not undergo any electrochemical reduction in any buffer in the potential range studied. The cyclic voltammetric response (at pH 9.00) of a representative carboxy amide, *o*-toluimale is given in Fig. 1. The electrochemical data for all the samples are collected in Table 1. From the absence of any electrochemical response for the succinic and phthalic analogues, it can be concluded that the two irreversible reduction waves, observed for maleic acid derivatives, are due to the electrochemical reduction of the C=C and that they are not due to the electrochemical reduction across the carbonyl group of the amide.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammogram of *o*-tolui-male ($2 \times 10^{-4}M$) at pH 9.0, at a scan rate of 50 of $mV s^{-1}$.

TABLE I—CYCLIC VOLTAMMETRIC DATA OF THE CARBOXYAMIDE SYSTEMS^a (HL; 1)

Compd.	pH								$D_0 \times 10^6$ mean $\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
	6.01		8.03		8.50		9.00		
			E_{P_1}, E_{P_2}						
anil-male	1.13	1.35	1.21	1.61	1.22	1.62	1.32	1.80	1.621
<i>o</i> -toli-male	1.14	1.38	1.23	1.62	1.24	1.63	1.33	1.82	1.612
<i>o</i> -anisi-male	1.15	1.41	1.25	1.69	1.28	1.65	1.36	1.85	1.622
<i>o</i> -Cl-anil-male	1.12	1.33	1.19	1.59	1.21	1.58	1.31	1.78	1.621

^aAll at $2 \times 10^{-4} M$ with buffer concentration at $0.01 M$; scan rate = 50 mV s^{-1} . All potentials are in V negative with respect to Ag/AgCl.

The electrochemical reduction potentials of the carbonyl groups in all these compounds, might be more negative than the hydrogen evolution potential. The cathodic drift of the observed peak potentials as pH is increased, indicates the involvement of H^+ ions in the electrochemical reduction.

Effect of scan rate on CV profiles : At lower scan rates the second peak is faint whereas it becomes increasingly prominent as the scan rate increased. This can be seen from the profiles shown in Fig. 2. From the studies of the effect of scan rate of peak current of the first and second peaks, it is concluded that the first reduction peak is nearly diffusion-controlled, whereas the second one is governed by the kinetics of the generation of the reducible species. These results indicate a successive electron transfer process, interluded by a parallel chemical reaction following the first electron transfer process, that the reducible species responsible for the second curve is generated from the first electron transfer process and that it is chemically unstable.

To arrive at the number of electrons involved in each of the successive electron transfer processes, different electrochemical approaches were followed. The differential pulse polarogram recorded for the sample solutions gave two peaks. Using the relation,

$$W_{1/2} = \frac{90.12}{n}$$

where $W_{1/2}$ is the width (mV) at half-height of the peak, the number of electrons (n) can be calculated. For the present compounds, $W_{1/2}$ was found to be $\sim 92.5 \text{ mV}$ for each of the reduction peaks, indicating that both the waves are characterised by one electron transfer processes. That the electron transfer processes involve one electron each, is confirmed by the constant potential coulometry performed at two set potentials; one after the first peak and the other after the second. The number of electrons obtained from the first setting is 1, whereas that from the second is 2. Based on this information and the observed data, an electron transfer mechanism (Scheme 1) can be suggested for the carboxy amide systems.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of *o*-tolui-male ($2 \times 10^{-4} M$) at different scan rates: (a) 10, (b) 20, (c) 50, (d) 100, (e) 200 and (f) 500 mV s^{-1} . All in 8.03 pH ammoniacal buffer.

where X is a substituent as shown in structure 1.

Scheme 1

The first electrochemical wave at $\sim (-) 1.20$ V is due to the electron transfer step I, and the second wave at $\sim (-) 1.70$ V is due to III. The free radical produced by I is unstable and undergoes a fast chemical dimerisation shown at step II. This step expends the free radical, which is the reducible species for step III, and hence the low intensity of the second CV peak at low scan rates. But when the scan rate is increased the electrochemical potential for the electron transfer process at step III is sooner reached than the depletion of the free radical through II and hence the improvement in peak height of the second wave at faster potential scans (Fig. 2). This mechanism is in close agreement with that reported for the electrochemical reduction of pure maleic acid⁷. The final proof for the above mechanism comes from the constant potential coulometric synthesis. Electrolysis at $(-) 1.80$ V followed by acidification resulted in the precipitation of a solid, which upon analysis was found to be identical with that of succinic based carboxy amides. But the electrolysis at $(-) 1.50$ V and acidification gave a colourless power different from the succinic analogue but whose elemental analysis was in agreement with the dimer in step II.

The mean values of the diffusion coefficients

of L^- evaluated from fast polarography, normal pulse polarography and cyclic voltammetry⁸ assuming that the first electron transfer step I is diffusion controlled, are collected in Table 1. The close agreement of the D_0 values obtained from these different methods for a given L^- in a given buffer, suggests that the first electron transfer step is diffusion-controlled. Additional proof for this assumption comes from the linearity of the plots of i vs C , where i is the i_d (diffusion current) in polarographic methods and i_p (peak current) in cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarography and C is concentration of the L^- species in the bulk. The smooth decrease in the D_0 values of the L^- species as X on the benzene ring, increases in size is on expected lines. The shift in the reduction potentials of the L^- at a given pH as X is altered, is worth commenting on. As the electron transfer processes take place across the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ of the maleic acid moiety, the nature of the inductive effect caused by the substituents on the phenyl ring of L^- will have definite effect on the reduction potentials. Substituents with positive inductive effect (such as CH_3 , OCH_3), would oppose electron transfer to the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ causing cathodic drift to the E_p 's vis-a-vis the unsubstituted system, anil-male, whereas the ones with negative inductive effect (such as Cl and NO_2), cause slight anodic drift. The facts that *o*-Cl anil-male has less negative and that *o*-tolui-male and *o*-anisi-male have more negative reduction potentials than anil-male run on these substituent-electronic effects.

At pH's more than 9.40, the carboxamide systems do not engage in any successive electron transfer processes (Scheme 1) and instead undergo a one-step two-electron irreversible reduction process, at a far higher negative potentials [$\sim (-) 1.90$ V]. The absence of Scheme 1 type reduction may be due to the poor concentration of H^+ ions at pHs greater than 9.00. The one-step two-electron transfer process at pHs lower than 9.00 might have been obscured by the overwhelming hydrogen evolution current.

However, the hydrogen evolution process is shifted to beyond (-)2.00 V in highly basic media of pH greater than 9.00, thus uncovering the one-step two-electron transfer process.

Experimental

All the electrochemical studies were performed on an EG & G PARC 264 A3 polarographic analyser/stripping voltammeter comprising of PARC 264 A polarographic analyser/stripping voltammeter 303A SMDE electrode assembly and a PARC RE 0150 X-Y recorder. The elemental analysis data were collected from a Carlo-Erba EA 1108 CHNS-O analyser coupled with Carlo-Erba DP 200 data processor. The three-electrode assembly consisted of a stationary (or dropping) mercury drop working electrode, platinum wire auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode.

N-Phenylmonoamide derivatives of 1,2-dicarboxylic acids (HL; **1**) were synthesised by mixing hot benzene solutions of aniline or any one from *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, anisidines and chloroanilines with that of any cyclic anhydrides from maleic, phthalic and succinic anhydrides in a 1 : 1 molar ratio⁴. The resulting compounds were purified by dissolving in sodium bicarbonate solution followed by regeneration upon acidification and by washing the precipitates. This process was repeated 2 or 3 times till a sharp melting point was ensured. The elemental analysis data of a few compounds (**1**) are as follows (theoretical percentage given in paranthesis) : (i) anil-male, C, 62.88 (62.82); H, 4.77 (4.71); N, 7.35 (7.33%); (ii) *o*-tolui-male, C, 64.41 (64.39); H, 5.40 (5.37); N, 6.89 (6.83%); (iii) *o*-anisi-male, C, 59.76 (59.73); H, 4.96 (4.98); N, 6.32 (6.35%).

The carboxyamide compounds (HL; **1**) were converted into millimolar NaL aqueous solutions by suspending weighed quantity of HL compound (**1**) in water (50 ml) followed by the addition of calculated volume of standard 0.01 M NaOH

solution. In a typical preparation, anil-male (0.02000 g, 0.10 mmole) was suspended in water and 0.01 M NaOH (10 ml) was added, and made upto 100 ml. The solution, as expected for an aqueous one of carboxylate salt containing an amide moiety, was observed to be only slightly basic at a pH of ~ 7.15.

Buffers of varying pHs were made following the literature procedures^{9,10} and were used as both supporting electrolytes and media of constant pH's. The electrochemical run was carried out by transferring the buffer (4 ml) and NaL (1 ml) solutions.

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